

Synthesis of Novel *N*-Substituted Phenothiazines and Piperazines as Potential Biologically Active Agents

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Phenothiazines have been utilised for pharmacological and biological activities¹. So it was of interest to synthesise some members of the group with a view to examine their biological activities.

A number of compounds have been prepared by the condensation of phenothiazine/diphenylamine/benzotriazole with $\text{ClCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}/\text{ClCH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ to yield the respective acids (**1a-f**). Compounds **1a-f** on reaction with SOCl_2 afforded the corresponding chlorides (**2a-f**), which were condensed separately with phenothiazine and piperazine to give **3a-f** and **3g-r** (Scheme 1). The compounds were characterised by microanalysis, and spectral data (Table 1). All the compounds have been screened for anthelmintic, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activities.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on an Acculab-10 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) at 90 MHz on a Varian CFT-20 instrument and mass spectra on a Jeol-D 300 spectrometer.

Phenothiazine-10-acetic acid (1a) : A solution of equimolar phenothiazine (10 g, 0.50 mol) and $\text{ClCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ (4.725 g, 0.05 mol) in Me_2CO was heated on a water-bath (30 min) and the resulting solid was crystallised from C_6H_6 , (76%), m.p. 158–60°. Other acetic/propionic acids (**1b-f**) were synthesised similarly (yields 57–78%) : **1b**, m.p. 190–95°; **c**, 42–44°; **d**, 55–57°; **e**, 50–52°; **f**, 54–56°.

Scheme 1

Phenothiazino-10-acetyl chloride (2a) : A solution of phenothiazino-10-acetic acid (10 g, 0.038 mol) in $\text{Me}_2\text{CO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_6$ (1 : 1) and SOCl_2 (5.68 ml, 0.076 mol) was refluxed for about 8 h on a water-bath. Excess of SOCl_2 was then distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from CHCl_3 , (77%), m.p. 168–70°. Other chlorides (yields 77–86%) were prepared in a similar manner : **2b**, m.p. 173–75°; **c**, 158–60°; **d**, 190–92°; **e**, 58–60°; **f**, 64–66°.

N-[(10-Phenothiazino)acetyl]phenothiazine (3a) : Equimolar solution of **2a** (3 g, 0.015 mol) in Me_2CO was added dropwise in an alkaline solution of phenothiazine (2.98 g, 0.015 mol) in Me_2CO

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3a-r)*

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	M.p. °C
3a	Phenothiazine	H	185–88
b	Phenothiazine	CH ₃	158–60
c	Diphenylamine	H	50–55
d	Diphenylamine	CH ₃	54–56
e	Benzotriazole	H	150–52
f	Benzotriazole	CH ₃	155–56
g	Phenothiazine	H	165–68
h	Phenothiazine	CH ₃	160–62
i	Diphenylamine	H	38–40
j	Diphenylamine	CH ₃	50–52
k	Benzotriazole	H	80–82
l	Benzotriazole	CH ₃	85–87
m	Phenothiazine	H	160–65
n	Phenothiazine	CH ₃	162–64
o	Diphenylamine	H	50–54
p	Diphenylamine	CH ₃	56–60
q	Benzotriazole	H	70–75
r	Benzotriazole	CH ₃	72–73

3a ν_{\max} 1 600, 1 480, 1 460, 1 240, 920, 745, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.90–2.80 (2H, CH₂), 7.40–6.00 (16H, ArH); m/z 438 (M^+ , 70), 240(30), 226(50), 212(14) and 198 (base peak 100%); 3c ν_{\max} 1 610, 1 485, 1 440, 1 235, 920, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.85–2.80 (2H, CH₂) and 8.50–6.70 (18H, ArH); m/z 408 (M^+ , 85), 240(70), 226(17), 210(55), 198 (base peak 100), 182(10) and 168(35%); 3h ν_{\max} 3 140, 2 900, 1 600, 1 465, 1 230, 850, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.50–1.40 (3H, CH₃), 2.05 (1H, H-bonded to N), 2.80–2.70 (8H, 4 \times CH₂), 4.35 (1H, CH) and 8.15–7.46 (8H, ArH); m/z 339 (M^+ , 80), 254(50), 226(14), 198 (base peak 100), 141(35), 113(10) and 85(30%); 3k ν_{\max} 3 140, 1 610, 1 585, 1 480, 1 330, 750 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.00 (1H, H-bonded to N), 2.85–2.80 (10H, 5 \times CH₂) and 8.20–7.40 (4H, ArH); m/z 245 (M^+ , 80), 160(60), 132(18), 118 (base peak 100), 113(15) and 85(34%); 3m ν_{\max} 1 610, 1 480, 1 330, 910, 650 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.85–2.80 (12H, 6 \times CH₂) and 8.30–6.80 (16H, ArH).

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

and stirred for about 6 h. The solid thus obtained was passed through a silica column, eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) and crystallised from C₆H₆, (53%). Other compounds (3b–r; yields 41–70%) were prepared similarly (Table 1).

Anthelmintic activity : The compounds were tested² against the experimental infection of *A. ceylanicum* in hamsters in rats and *H. nana* in mice. Mebendazole was used as a standard

drug which killed 100% worm of *A. ceylanicum* at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg \times 3 and *H. nana* at dose of 250 mg/kg. Compounds 3g, 3h, 3k and 3l eliminated 42–70% worms at the same doses.

Anti-inflammatory activity : The activity was evaluated by the reported method³. The degree of protection provided by compounds 3a–r at 50–100 mg/kg p.o. against carrageenan induced rat paw oedema ranged from 3.00 to 39.39% protection. Compounds 3a, 3b, 3m and 3n (30–40%) were comparable with phenylbutazone (30 mg/kg; 45.45%).

Antimicrobial activity : Compounds 3a–r were screened for antimicrobial activity by filter paper disc method⁴. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ using bacteria *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *S. typhi* and fungi *A. niger*, *P. crysogenum*, *T. mentagrophytes* and *C. albicans*. Compounds 3a, 3f, 3m and 3n exhibited appreciable activity.

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